

The Effect of Two-Way Conflict on Work Engagement of SPBU PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya

Hafid Kholidi Hadi

Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Surabaya

E-mail: hafidhadi@unesa.ac.id

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Abstract: By using the theory of suitability and resource conservation as a theoretical basis, this study aims to propose and test a research model that investigates two-way conflict (work-family conflict and family-work conflict) on work engagement. The data were collected from 60 employees of PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya, Indonesia, one week apart in two waves which were used to assess the above-mentioned relationship through multiple linear regression on SPSS 23. The results showed that work-family conflict and family-work conflict respectively did not partially affect the work engagement of the employees of the gas station of PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya. In addition, work-family conflict and family-work conflict together (simultaneously) also do not affect employee work engagement. This study contributes to current knowledge by investigating the interrelationship of two-way conflict with work engagement.

Keywords: Gas Station, Work-Family Conflict, Family-Work Conflict, Work Engagement

1. Introduction

In today's competitive environment, many service companies find the important role of frontline employees (FLEs) service processes (Karatepe & Karadas, 2016). According to Spacey (2015), FLE is an employee who interacts directly with customers. This is usually in contrast to back-office employees who may never meet a customer. The following are typical examples of FLEs: customer service, sales, marketing, business units, consultants, and operations.

FLE often experiences work-family conflict (WFC) and family-work conflict (FWC), which are two stressors in work-family relationships (Choi & Kim, 2012; Karatepe, 2013a). WFC refers to "a form of dual role conflict in which the general demands, time spent, and pressure created by work interfere with the performance of family-related responsibilities" and FWC refers to "a form of dual role conflict in which the general demands of, time spent on and tensions created by the family interfere with the implementation of work-related responsibilities" (Netemeyer et al., 1996: 401). If FLE cannot balance work (family) and family (work) responsibilities, they cannot be involved in their work and show dissatisfaction with life in general. It seems that management should consider the importance of a match between employees' abilities and job demands (Edwards, 1991).

FLE is the main actor in the service delivery process and plays an important role in customer satisfaction (Karatepe & Karadas, 2016). Despite this recognition, these employees

are still plagued by problems arising from conflicts in the work-family interface (Karatepe, 2013a; Zhao et al., 2014). In these circumstances, management must find individuals who can meet the demands of front-line service jobs.

Many studies have shown that job resources encourage work engagement (WE) which refers to "a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption" (Schaufeli et al., 2002: 74). This means that employees who work in a resourceful environment feel excited, enthusiastic, and absorbed by their work (Karatepe & Karadas, 2016). However, stressful and demanding situations can erode employee WE (Coetzee & De Villiers, 2010). Therefore, our study measures the effects of WFC and FWC simultaneously on WE. This is due to the lack of empirical research on the relationship between stressors and WE (Burke et al., 2013; Karatepe, 2013b) and between conflicts in the work-family interface and WE (De Simone et al., 2014). It is also proven in the meta-analytic investigation of Crawford et al., (2010) that the dominant empirical study did not attribute stress demands or triggers to WE, even though there was a true relationship between them.

One of the fields of work that needs to pay attention to the things mentioned above, especially the work engagement of their employees is a company engaged in the service sector. One of them is PT. Pertamina Retail, where this company is a subsidiary of PT. Pertamina Persero has the main task of selling and distributing Fuel Oil (BBM) to the public by building and establishing a Public Fuel Filling Station (SPBU). However, the problem here is that the work engagement of employees of the company can be seen and felt directly by consumers or customers who buy products or refuel their vehicles there because employees are in direct contact with customers. Most of the time, consumers can pay attention directly to the enthusiasm, dedication, and attachment of these workers in doing their work, so that work engagement at this company needs to be maintained and what can influence it.

Furthermore, PT. Pertamina Retail currently has implemented the take line "PASTI PRIMA" which guarantees customers that the service at the fueling station there is the best. So that if the work engagement there is low, it will tarnish the company's image. Similar to the case at Public Refueling Stations or SPBU which are managed by the private sector, the employees are often very visible that they do not feel tied to their work. As reported by Gemantara.com (2020), there is often bad service at private gas stations which can even harm consumers, and according to researchers, this needs to be avoided and prevented to maintain the integrity of PT. Pertamina Retail itself.

This study examines employees who work at Public Refuelling Stations (SPBU). As many of us know, gas station employees often experience conflicts between work-family and family-work roles due to inappropriate timing and the emotional demands of work-family relationships. Therefore this research aims to identify the relationship between the effect of two-way conflict (work-family conflict and family-work conflict) on the work engagement of PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya.

1.1. Work-Family Conflict (WFC) and Family-Work Conflict (FWC)

The conceptual approach taken in this study is based on the premise that WFC and FWC are a form of conflict that is different but related roles (Netemeyer et al., 1996: 401). Multiple role conflict has been viewed as a form of conflict in which "the role pressures associated with

membership in one organization are conflicted with the pressure emanating from membership in another" (Kahn et al., 1964: 20). From a work-family and family-work perspective, this type of conflict reflects the extent to which the role responsibilities of the work and family domains are incompatible, that is, "participation in (family) work becomes more difficult because of family participation (work) roles" (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985: 77). Thus, the demands of one role make the performance of other roles more difficult (Katz & Kahn, 1978).

Although several WFC and FWC sources have been identified, most researchers agree that the general demands of a role, the time devoted to a particular role, and the strain generated by a particular role are elements of the WFC and FWC domains (Netemeyer et al., 1996: 401). The general requirements of a role refer to the responsibilities, requirements, expectations, duties, and commitments associated with the given role. (These terms have been used interchangeably throughout the literature).

Time-based conflict occurs when the amount of time devoted to the work- (family) role interferes with the family- (work) responsibilities that are being established. In particular, excessive work (family) time conflicts can make it difficult to comply with family (work) responsibilities. Tension-based conflict occurs when the tensions created by work (family) roles interfere with the performance of family (work) responsibilities. For example, the irritability and anxiety created by work interfere with the performance of family relationships and vice versa (Netemeyer et al., 1996: 401).

Thus, we use the following definitions according to Netemeyer et al., (1996) to guide our scale development. The WFC is a form of dual role conflict in which general demands, the time spent, and the pressure created by work interfere with the performance of family-related responsibilities. FWC is a form of dual role conflict in which general demands, time devoted to and tensions created by the family interfere with the performance of work-related responsibilities.

1.2. Work Engagement (WE)

Work engagement is defined as "a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind characterized by passion, dedication, and absorption" (Schaufeli et al., 2002: 74). Furthermore, work engagement is not "a momentary state, like emotion, ... [but] refers to a more persistent motivational state that does not focus on a particular object, event, individual or behavior" (Salanova & Schaufeli, 2008: 118). Research on job engagement focuses on the main dimensions of passion, dedication, and absorption. Passion involves the energy and level of individual resilience, which is very helpful in maintaining a positive perspective while working (Salanova & Schaufeli, 2008). Dedication requires how much enthusiasm, pride, and inspiration individuals have for their work. A higher level of dedication allows individuals to better identify with their work (Salanova & Schaufeli, 2008). Absorption is the extent to which people become engrossed in their work; higher absorption rates can cause individuals to become so engaged that they find it difficult to separate and detach from their jobs (Salanova & Schaufeli, 2008). Work engagement has been described as a condition of fulfilling continuous positive motivational feelings characterized by a high level of involvement and enthusiasm about one's job (Fazlurrahman et al., 2020).

According to Salanova & Schaufeli (2008), the existence of work engagement between employees is an indicator of their intrinsic motivation. This is consistent with the theory of self-determination (Ryan & E.L., 2000), which emphasizes the social context in which employees are proactive, empowered, and involved as well as the psychological climate aspects of organizational culture previously described by Parker et al., (2003). Employees who are engaged in their work feel energized, they experience a sense of pride in what they do, time at work flies by and they have a sense of personal satisfaction (Biggs A & Barbour, 2013; Ryan & Deci, 2001; Saks, 2006). However, people's lives transcend their jobs. Sonnentag et al., (2008) observed that a key factor in employee engagement is the ability to psychologically 'shut off' or disconnect from work during non-work time. Usually, psychological detachment involves social relationships and people's activities such as hanging out with friends or pursuing hobbies or other interests. In addition, most employees have other responsibilities that must be taken care of and must exist psychologically, such as child support and/or other family matters, household duties, and sports. Sonnentag et al., (2008) found that employees who were unable to achieve release from their jobs experienced a corresponding decrease in their work engagement. It is therefore observed that the long-hours work culture described by a number of researchers (Timms et al., 2015; Rahman et al., 2020) has the potential to erode employee engagement with work.

1.3. Hypothesis Development

Conservation of Resources (COR) theory is used as a theoretical basis for developing a relationship between the two directions of conflict and WE. In particular, the COR theory states that objects, conditions, personal characteristics, and energy are resources that individuals seek to acquire, maintain and protect (Hobfoll, 1989). Based on the COR theory, Shaffer et al., (2001: 100) state, "[...] Excessive demands and/or insufficient resources in a particular role domain or between domains can result in negative affective and dysfunctional behaviour." Therefore, we argue that petrol station employees often experience stress, and work in an environment where job resources such as rewards, autonomy and career opportunities are scarce (Karatepe, 2013b; Kusluvan et al., 2010). Under these conditions, they are not can manage their responsibilities and face conflicts between work (family) and family (work) domains. As a result, these employees tend to be less energetic and enthusiastic, and absorbed by their work.

There are limited studies on the effect of job demands or two-way conflict on WE. However, the results of this study are mixed. In particular, the study of Montgomery et al., (2003) documented that WFC reduced WE among Dutch newspaper managers, while FWC had nothing to do with WE. One empirical study among employees of a small South African manufacturing company showed that job demands did not contribute to WE (Coetzer & Rothmann, 2007). Coetzee & De Villiers (2010) investigations among employees of South African financial institutions suggested that role ambiguity alleviated WE. In a study conducted with employees of Italian public service organizations, De Simone et al., (2014) found that FWC was negatively related to WE, whereas WFC was not.

The direct observation that can be made from the empirical study presented above is that there are various findings that relate to the concurrent effects of WFC and FWC on WE. In addition, Schaufeli & Bakker (2004) argue that job resources were closely related to WE,

while job demands were closely related to fatigue or burnout. However, there are empirical studies that report that job demands were significantly related to WE (Coetzee & De Villiers, 2010; Karatepe, 2013b). It is also underlined in the meta-analytic study of Crawford et al., (2010) that there was a true relationship between stress demands or triggers and WE, even though most researchers thought there was not. In other words, their meta-analytic investigation found that job demands were significantly related to WE, whereas the dominant empirical study did not link job demands to WE. Based on the COR theory and its limited findings, it is suspected that:

- H1. *Work-family conflict has a negative effect on work engagement.*
- H2. *Family-work conflict has a negative effect on work engagement.*

Figure 1.
Conceptual Framework

2. Research Method

This research is quantitative. This study used a non-probability sampling technique, with a total sampling approach or census (Ghozali, 2016). This study used primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from offline questionnaires that were distributed directly, and secondary data were collected from scientific articles, books, and other sources related to the theory of work-family conflict, family-work conflict, and work engagement.

The population in this study were employees of the General Fuel Filling Station (SPBU) PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya (Jl. Ketintang Madya No.53, Ketintang, Kec. Gayungan, Surabaya City, East Java and Jl. Raya Jemursari No.123, Jemur Wonosari, Kec. Wonocolo, Surabaya City, East Java) a total of 60 employees. Roscoe (1975) proposes the following rule of thumb for determining sample size: sample sizes greater than 30 and less than 500 are appropriate for most studies (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 264). In this study, 60 collected respondents were used as the final sample of the study.

The work-family conflict variable is measured by a 9-item statement developed by researchers referring to (Haslam et al., 2014; Majekodunmi, 2017). The variable family-work conflict was measured using a 10-item statement developed by researchers referring to (Haslam et al., 2014; Majekodunmi, 2017). Meanwhile, in measuring work engagement using a 9-item statement developed by researchers referring to (Schaufeli et al., 2006). All items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree), with respondents indicating whether they agree or disagree with each statement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 215). To estimate the model of the relationship between variables, this study refers to the use of the Multiple Linear Regression analysis techniques with the help of SPSS (Statistical Programs for Social Science) software version 23.

The selected respondents met the sample criteria previously determined by the researcher. The result, 90% of men and 10% of women with details of 50% aged 21-30 years; 28.3% aged 31-40 years; 18.3% aged 41-50 years; and 3.3% were > 51 years old. Overall, 41.7% were operators; 5% of them are salespeople; 8.3% of them are sales admin bright; 6.7% of which are cleaning services; 1.7% of them are customer service; 11.7% of them are security; 3.3% of them are cashiers; 11.7% of them are shift heads; 5% of whom are supervisors; 3.3% of them are admins; and 1.7% of which is nitrogen.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Validity and Reliability Test

The validity test in this study was carried out by comparing the calculated R-value with the r-table for $(df) = n - 2$ (Ghozali, 2016). Thus, for $(df) = 60 - 2 = 58$, we get an r-table of 0.2542. Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the total corrected item value of each statement item is greater than the r-table value, namely 0.2542 so that all statements can be said to be valid. Cronbach's alpha value ranges from 0.911 to 0.930 and is more than 0.70, so it can be said to be reliable.

Table 1.
Validity and Reliability of Variables

Variable and scale item all indicators	R-Table	Correlations	Reliability	Mean
<i>Work-Family Conflict</i>			0.926	1.30
My job demands interfere with my home and family life.	0.2542	0.860		1.27
My job prevents me from spending quality time with my family.	0.2542	0.867		1.35
There is no time left at the end of the day to do the things I love at home.	0.2542	0.939		1.35
The amount of time my job takes makes it difficult to fulfill family responsibilities.	0.2542	0.868		1.25
The things I want to do at home are not done because of the demands of my job.	0.2542	0.822		1.25
My family is neglected because of my work commitments.	0.2542	0.790		1.27
Due to a work-related assignment, I have to make changes to my plans for family activities.	0.2542	0.653		1.62
My job has a negative impact on my family life.	0.2542	0.664		1.18
Work often leaves me irritable or irritable at home.	0.2542	0.791		1.13
<i>Family-Work Conflict</i>			0.911	1.22
My family/partner's demands interfere with work-related activities.	0.2542	0.782		1.25
My work performance is impaired because of my personal and family commitments.	0.2542	0.785		1.25
I have to put off doing things at work because of the demands of my time at home.	0.2542	0.777		1.20
Family-related concerns or responsibilities often bother me at work.	0.2542	0.721		1.30
Things I want to do at work go unresolved because of demands from my family or spouse/partner.	0.2542	0.766		1.25
My family brings a negative impact on my daily work.	0.2542	0.845		1.18

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Variable and scale item all indicators	R-Tabel	Correlations	Reliability	Mean
My domestic life interferes with my responsibilities at work such as leaving for work on time, completing daily tasks, and working overtime.	0.2542	0.699		1.28
If I didn't have a family, I would be a better employee.	0.2542	0.656		1.18
Family-related tensions interfere with my ability to perform work-related tasks.	0.2542	0.734		1.13
It is difficult to concentrate on work because I am so tired of family responsibilities.	0.2542	0.738		1.15
<i>Work Engagement</i>			0.930	4.23
At work, I feel full of energy.	0.2542	0.852		4.27
At work, I feel strong	0.2542	0.843		4.33
I am enthusiastic about my work.	0.2542	0.878		4.52
My work inspires me	0.2542	0.749		4.38
When I wake up in the morning, I feel like working.	0.2542	0.834		4.37
I feel good when I work intensely.	0.2542	0.891		4.40
I am proud of the work I do	0.2542	0.767		4.52
I am immersed in my work	0.2542	0.724		3.40
I enjoy it when I work	0.2542	0.796		3.88

Source: SPSS 23

From the results of respondents' answers based on the Likert scale answer selection criteria then interpreted using the three-box method, then the range of five must be divided by three to produce a range of 1,33 (1,00 - 2,33 = low; 2,34 - 3,67 = moderate; 3,68 - 5,00 = high), it is then used as the basis for the interpretation of the mean value of the variable (Ferdinand, 2006). Based on the respondent's assessment of the research variables (Work-Family Conflict = 1,30; Family - Work Conflict = 1,22; Work Engagement = 4,23), one latent variable is in a low category while one latent variable is in the high category.

3.1.2. Classic Assumption Test

The normality test in this study also used non-parametric statistical analysis One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S test) at 5% alpha. If the significance value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is greater than 0,05, it means the data is normal (Ghozali, 2016).

Table 2.
Normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov)

	Normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov)	Unstandardized Residual
N		60
Normal	.0000000	.0000000
Parameters ^{a,b}	6.09507872	2.58042308
Most Extreme Differences	.124	.132
	.107	.115
	-.124	-.132
Test Statistic		.124
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.123 ^c

Source: SPSS 23

Based on the normality statistical test in Table 2., it shows that Kolmogorov-Smirnov is 0,124 and a significance is 0,123 so that the significance value of 0,123 is greater than 0,05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

The multicollinearity test can be seen from the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF). The cut-off value is commonly used to indicate multicollinearity if the tolerance value is $\leq 0,10$ or the same as the VIF value ≥ 10 (Ghozali, 2016).

Several ways can be used to determine the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity, one of which is using the Glejser test. The basis for decision making in this Glejser Test is that if the t-count value is smaller than the t-table and the significant value is greater than 0,05, the regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity. If the t-count is smaller than the t-table and the significant value is smaller than 0,05, then this regression model experiences heteroscedasticity (Ghozali, 2016).

The basis for decision making in the linearity test is based on probability, that is, if the probability value is $> 0,05$, then the relationship between variables X and Y is linear, however, if the probability value is $< 0,05$, then the relationship between variables X and Y is not linear.

Table 3.
Multicollinearity, Heteroscedasticity, and Linearity

Variable	Multicollinearity				Heteroscedasticity		Linearity
	VIF	Tolerance	Beta	T	T-Tabel	Significance	Significance
X1	4.952	.202	-.043	-.147	-.242	.810	.933
X2	4.952	.202	-.115	-.396	-.536	.594	.871

Source: SPSS 23

Based on the data in Table 3, it can be seen that all independent variables have met the requirements to pass the multicollinearity test, namely a tolerance value greater than 0,10 and a VIF value not more than 10.

Table 3, also shows that the results of the Glejser Test regression model do not contain heteroscedasticity. This can be seen from the existence of independent variables which have a significance above 0,05. And the t-count value is smaller than the t-table ($-0,242 < 1,671$) for the X1 variable and the X2 variable ($-0,536 < 1,671$).

Table 3, also presents the results of all variables having a significant value greater than 0.05, which means that there is a significant linear relationship between the independent variables (X1 and X2) on the dependent variable (Y).

3.1.3. Multiple Linear Regression

Table 4 presents the output of multiple linear regression testing that has been carried out, in this case, the results of the Significant Test for Individual Parameters / Hypotheses (T Statistical Test) will be presented; Simultaneous Significance Test (Test F); and the coefficient of determination (R2).

Table 4.
Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Partial			Simultaneous			Determination
	Unstandardized Coefficients			Model	F	Sig.	R Square
	β	Sig					
(Constant)	41.292	.000		Regression	.701	.500 ^b	.024
1 X1	-.066	.884		Residual			
X2	-.201	.693		Total			

Source: SPSS 23

The significance value of the work-family conflict variable shows a value of 0,884 which means it is greater than 0,05 and the coefficient value of the work-family conflict variable is -0,066; so it means that partially work-family conflict has no effect on work engagement; and it can be interpreted that the high work-family conflict experienced by employees does not affect employee work engagement, so it can be concluded that H1 is rejected.

Moreover, the significance value of the family-work conflict variable shows a value of 0,693 which means it is greater than 0,05 and the coefficient value of the work-family conflict variable is -0,201; so it means that partially family-work conflict has no effect on work engagement, and it can be interpreted that the high family-work conflict experienced by employees does not affect employee work engagement, so it can be concluded that H2 is rejected.

Based on Table 4, it is known that the significance level is 0,500 greater than 0,05. It can be concluded that the work-family conflict and family-work conflict variables together (simultaneously) do not affect the work engagement variable.

Based on Table 4, it is also known that the coefficient of determination has an R-Square value of 0,024. This shows that the size of the independent variables in this study (work-family conflict and family-work conflict) can explain 2,4% of the work engagement variable, while 97,6% is explained by other variables outside of this study.

3.2. Discussion

Partially, the work-family conflict did not affect work engagement, the high work-family conflict experienced by employees did not affect employee work engagement. Based on the respondents' answers to the research variables, the work-family conflict variable with an average answer of 1,30 was in a low category, while the work engagement variable with an average answer of 4,23 was in the high category. From the respondents' answers based on the descriptive results of each research variable, it is evident that the employees who work at the PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya had proven not to experience a form of dual role conflict in which public demands, time spent, and pressure created by work interfered with the implementation of family-related responsibilities. The results of variable descriptions also prove that the level of work involvement of each employee was very good, this can happen because the existing resources in the workplace have supported each employee well so that this does not have an impact on the poor relationship between the employee and his family. The work resources in question include the absence of job demands which result in disruption of family life. In addition, based on conditions in the field, even though sometimes some employees had to go home at night and made the partner feel that there was not enough time to spend a moment together, giving understanding to the partner was one of the solutions to minimize this, so that often the partner would give good feedback in the form of giving more attention, motivation, and enthusiasm to your husband or wife who is working. Not infrequently, sometimes the spouses of several employees often came to the office during break time to send food or just provide support so that it could increase the level of involvement during their busy work.

Partially, the family-work conflict did not affect work engagement, the high family-work conflict experienced by employees did not affect employee work engagement. Based on the respondents' answers to the research variables, the family-work conflict variable with an average answer of 1,22 was in a low category, while the work engagement variable with an average answer of 4,23 was in the high category. From the respondents' answers based on the descriptive results of each research variable, it is evident that the employees who work at the PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya proved that they did not experience a form of dual role conflict in which public demands, time spent, and tensions created by the family interfered with the implementation of work-related responsibilities. The fact that FWC did not play a significant role in work engagement may be related to the fact that the results were job-specific. Such a conclusion is supported by the fact that there was no demand for housing which indicates any direct relationship with the outcome. In addition, it is possible the respondents in the sample (who are mostly men) did not bear the burden of housing demands to work with them. In addition, based on conditions in the field, although sometimes some employees were unable to complete their work on time due to several conflicts they had with their spouses, this did not have a very detrimental impact on the company. This means that even though some employees experience difficulties with their work, employees can complete the work while still taking full responsibility for completing it.

The results of this study indicate that job resources played an important role in the level of employee involvement in service or service companies. It seems that these employees are more energetic and enthusiastic when the organization provides the necessary resources. Four types of resources, namely organizational support, growth opportunities, social support, and advancement opportunities, seem to predict the work engagement of these employees. Organizational support such as supportive leader relationships, communication, information, clarity of roles and participation, and growth opportunities that include factors such as variations in employment, learning opportunities, and independence, play a more important role in increasing job engagement.

There are several important implications for business practice. First, management must create a family-supportive work environment where there are family-friendly benefits (e.g., financial support for life insurance, subsidized on-site child care services) and supervisors who support the family (Karatepe, 2013a). However, management must ensure that when employees take advantage of these benefits, this will not jeopardize their current career in the organization. Second, management must establish a special training program to teach supervisory employees how to be a supervisor who supports the family and acts as a mentor. As a result, they can help employees deal with work and family issues. Management can also organize special workshops where employees and their family members can attend. In this workshop, management should seek advice from employees and family members on how to reduce two-way conflict. Getting feedback from employees and family members makes them feel more valued. Finally, there is a need for a work environment that has resources consisting of adequate high-performance work practices such as rewards and empowerment. This is important because such a work environment tends to motivate employees to display positive work results (Yavas et al., 2010). This resourceful work environment can also lead to the retention of employees who remain engaged in their jobs.

4. Conclusion

This study examines the effect of two-way conflict (work-family conflict and family-work conflict) on work engagement among PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya. The results showed that work-family conflict and family-work conflict partially did not affect the work engagement of PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya. In addition, work-family conflict and family-work conflict together (simultaneously) also do not affect the work engagement of the employees of the PT. Pertamina Retail Ketintang and Jemursari Surabaya.

Our study is not without limits. First, our study measures the effects of WFC and FWC on WE due to the lack of empirical evidence in this research stream. However, participation in multiple roles can also yield many benefits that can go beyond the costs associated with work and family roles (Karatepe & Bekteshi, 2008). Our study used a temporal separation that included a one-week time lag to minimize the potential risk of general method bias. Moreover, the relatively small number of samples limits our generalizability of this study.

Therefore, further research is expected to increase the number of research samples and must examine the relationship in the research model through data that will be collected over a longer period than was done in this study. Future research might be attempted to expand the reach of the population at the SPBU PT. Pertamina Retail to get clearer data results. Given the low value of the R² test result or the coefficient of determination, further research is expected to consider other variables such as perceived organizational support, person-environment fit, job demand, and job satisfaction. In closing, replication in other service settings such as airlines, hoteliers, and banks is required to cross-validate our results and expand the database in this research stream.

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